

RURAL LIFE IN FRENCH LITERATURE OF THE 19TH CENTURY

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Annotation: The article covers significant points about French literature of the 19th century. Moreover, in the article special features of French literature and main peculiarities of rural life description in that century. On the other hand, facts about famous creators of the French literature were noted.

Key words: *present conjuncture, pejorative terms, divergent, French cultural landscape, Contemporary approaches, romantic images, ethical ideas.*

The end of the second millennium seems as appropriate a moment as any for a survey of a thousand years of French literature. But the task of the historian is made more, not less difficult by the present conjuncture. It is not simply that there is now more French literature to account for than ever before, but that there is no common agreement about what qualifies as 'literature' French literature enjoyed enormous international prestige and success in the 19th century. The first part of the century was dominated by Romanticism, until around the mid-century Realism emerged, at least partly as a reaction. In the last half of the century, "naturalism", "parnassian" poetry, and "symbolism", among other styles, were often competing tendencies at the same time. Some writers did form into literary groups defined by a name and a program or manifesto. In other cases, these expressions were merely pejorative terms given by critics to certain writers or have been used by modern literary historians to group writers of divergent projects or methods. Nevertheless, these labels can be useful in describing broad historical developments in the arts.

19th-century French literature concerns the developments in French literature during a dynamic period in French history that saw the rise of Democracy and the fitful end of Monarchy and Empire. The period covered spans the following political regimes: Napoleon Bonaparte's Consulate (1799–1804) and Empire (1804–1814), the Restoration under Louis XVIII and Charles X (1814–1830), the July Monarchy under Louis Philippe d'Orléans (1830–1848), the Second Republic (1848–1852), the Second Empire under Napoleon III (1852–1871), and the first decades of the Third Republic (1871–1940). At the beginning of the nineteenth century the French cultural landscape was ready for the progressive independence of the literary and artistic field from institutional and bourgeois dogmas. For Jean-Paul Sartre the process of autonomisation of literature from bourgeois ideology was completed about halfway through the nineteenth century: “Après 1850 iln’y a plus moyen de dissimuler la contradiction profonde qui oppose l’idéologie bourgeoise aux exigences de la littérature.” According to Pierre Bourdieu, in nineteenth-century France there was a progressive political, religious and institutional liberation of all cultural products.⁷ The process of autonomisation of the visual arts was slower but soon followed. The independence of cultural products from bourgeois ideology and state domination brought with it the beginnings of the competition between the visual and literary arts as they fought for the domination of the artistic field, thereby contributing to the separation of the fields of art and literature. Contemporary approaches and the current practice of interdisciplinary studies in French art and literature tend to take a theoretical approach. Instead, this book proposes to look at the relationship between art and literature, by focusing on specific artworks and books. By means of a series of case studies, chosen from key moments throughout the nineteenth century, our aim is to provide a focused analysis of specific examples of this relationship, revealing both its multifaceted nature as well as offering a panorama of the development of this ongoing and increasingly complex

cultural relationship.

From the 1860s on, critics increasingly speak of literary "Naturalism". The expression is imprecise, and was frequently used disparagingly to characterize authors whose chosen subject matter was taken from the working classes and who portrayed the misery and harsh conditions of real life. Many of the "naturalist" writers took a radical position against the excesses of romanticism and strove to use scientific and encyclopedic precision in their novels (Zola spent months visiting coal mines for his *Germinal*, and even the arch-realist Flaubert was famous for his years of research for historical details). Hippolyte Taine supplied much of the philosophy of naturalism: he believed that every human being was determined by the forces of heredity and environment and by the time in which he lived. The influence of certain Norwegian, Swedish and Russian writers gave an added impulse to the naturalistic movement.

The novels and short stories of Guy de Maupassant are often tagged with the label "naturalist", although he clearly followed the realist model of his teacher and mentor, Flaubert. Maupassant used elements derived from the gothic novel in stories like *Le Horla*. This tension between portrayal of the contemporary world in all its sordidness, detached irony and the use of romantic images and themes would also influence the symbolists (see below) and would continue to the 20th century. Naturalism is most often associated with the novels of Émile Zola in particular his *Les Rougon-Macquart* novel cycle, which includes *Germinal*, *L'Assommoir*, *Nana*, *Le Ventre de Paris*, *La Bête humaine*, and *L'Œuvre* (The Masterpiece), in which the social success or failure of two branches of a family is explained by physical, social and hereditary laws. Other writers who have been labeled naturalists include: Alphonse Daudet, Jules Vallès, Joris-Karl Huysmans (later a leading "decadent" and rebel against naturalism), [1] Edmond de Goncourt and his brother Jules de Goncourt, and (in a very different vein) Paul Bourget. The naturalist tendency to see life without

illusions and to dwell on its more depressing and sordid aspects appears in an intensified degree in the immensely influential poetry of Charles Baudelaire, but with profoundly romantic elements derived from the Byronic myth of the anti-hero and the romantic poet, and the world-weariness of the "mal du siècle", etc. Similar elements occur in the novels of Jules Barbey d'Aurevilly.

The poetry of Baudelaire and much of the literature in the latter half of the century (or "fin de siècle") were often characterized as "decadent" for their lurid content or moral vision. In a similar vein, Paul Verlaine used the expression "poète maudit" ("accursed poet") in 1884 to refer to a number of poets like Tristan Corbière, Stéphane Mallarmé and Arthur Rimbaud who had fought against poetic conventions and suffered social rebuke or had been ignored by the critics. But with the publication of Jean Moréas Symbolist Manifesto in 1886, it was the term symbolism which was most often applied to the new literary environment. The writers Stéphane Mallarmé, Paul Verlaine, Paul Valéry, Joris-Karl Huysmans, Arthur Rimbaud, Jules Laforgue, Jean Moréas, Gustave Kahn, Albert Samain, Jean Lorrain, Rémy de Gourmont, Pierre Louÿs, Tristan Corbière, Henri de Régnier, Villiers de l'Isle-Adam, Stuart Merrill, René Ghil, Saint-Pol-Roux, Oscar-Vladislas de Milosz, Albert Giraud, Emile Verhaeren, Georges Rodenbach and Maurice Maeterlinck and others have been called symbolists, although each author's personal literary project was unique.

The symbolists often share themes that parallel Schopenhauer's aesthetics and notions of will, fatality and unconscious forces. The symbolists often used themes of sex (often through the figure of the prostitute), the city, irrational phenomena (delirium, dreams, narcotics, alcohol), and sometimes a vaguely medieval setting. The tone of symbolism is highly variable, at times realistic, imaginative, ironic or detached, although on the whole the symbolists did not stress moral or ethical ideas. In poetry, the symbolist procedure—as typified by Paul Verlaine—was to use subtle suggestion instead of precise

statement (rhetoric was banned) and to evoke moods and feelings by the magic of words and repeated sounds and the cadence of verse (musicality) and metrical innovation. Some symbolists explored the use of free verse. The use of leitmotifs, medieval settings and the notion of the complete work of art (blending music, visuals and language) in the works of the German composer Richard Wagner also had a profound impact on these writers.

Stéphane Mallarmé's profound interest in the limits of language as an attempt at describing the world, and his use of convoluted syntax, and in his last major poem *Un coup de dés*, the spacing, size and position of words on the page were important modern breakthroughs that continue to preoccupy contemporary poetry in France. Arthur Rimbaud's prose poem collection *Illuminations* are among the first free verse poems in French; his biographically inspired poem *Une saison en enfer* (A Season in Hell) was championed by the Surrealists as a revolutionary modern literary act (the same work would play an important role in the New York City punk scene in the 1970s). The infernal images of the prose poem *Les Chants de Maldoror* by Isidore Ducasse, Comte de Lautréamont would have a similar impact. The crisis of language and meaning in Mallarmé and the radical vision of literature, life and the political world in Rimbaud are to some degree the cornerstones of the "modern" and the radical experiments of Dada, Surrealism and Theatre of the Absurd (to name a few) in the 20th century.

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